

UNIQUE PSYCHOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF FAIRY TALE THERAPY IN OVERCOMING FEAR THAT AFFECTS THE MENTAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN

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Abstract. This article presents current issues of insurance situations in preschool and primary school age, their causes, psycho-correctional possibilities for prevention and elimination.

Key words: fear, internal experiences, emotion, anxiety, therapeutic activity, fairy tale therapy, the beginnings of trust, empathy, paralinguistics, cognitive field.

УНИКАЛЬНЫЕ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ СКАЗОЧНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ В ПРЕОДОЛЕНИИ СТРАХА, ВЛИЯЮЩЕГО НА ПСИХИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ ДЕТЕЙ

Аннотация. В статье представлены актуальные вопросы страховых ситуаций в дошкольном и младшем школьном возрасте, их причины, психокоррекционные возможности профилактики и устранения.

Ключевые слова: страх, внутренние переживания, эмоция, тревога, терапевтическая деятельность, сказкотерапия, зачатки доверия, эмпатия, паралингвистика, когнитивное поле.

In our developing society, much attention is paid to the issue of raising a healthy generation and perfect people. By preparing the youth of our republic, who are following their own path of development thanks to independence, and educating them in the spirit of the times. is one of the urgent and priority tasks of today. Currently, the reforms being implemented in our republic are focused on the spiritual appearance and personal development of youth. As is known, the current discussion of the science of psychology is centered around the sphere of the human psyche, which organizes its manifestation and development. Psychology organizes the inner world of a conscious subject - a person. To fully imagine the human psyche, it is necessary to understand the course of mental processes, the ability to express internal experiences (feelings, thoughts, emotions). It is known that fear is considered one of the most dangerous emotions and has a negative impact on the mental health of children of preschool and primary school age. As a result, the effectiveness of the education system decreases. Therefore, the problem of fear and anxiety in

children of preschool and primary school age is very relevant today.

From the first period of life, the child is afraid of everything new, strangers, as well as unfamiliar animals. Fairy tales are especially interesting and valuable for children, as they are a special means of psychological education for overcoming such fears in children. Through a fairy tale, a child learns to distinguish between good and evil, good and evil. The most important thing is that in their minds the features of overcoming fear are formed, without worrying about various dangers and difficulties. Fairytale therapy is one of the most effective areas of psychology, which helps adults and children communicate in the same language. With the help of accompanied stories, it is easier for adults to explain complex things to a child, approach him and help him solve the problem.

Fairytale therapy is a reliable support for children experiencing behavioral problems or stress. Also, fairytale therapy is a pleasant method that is positively perceived by children without lectures and the colorfulness of the interesting adventures of the characters. In addition to the therapeutic effect, fairy tales have a general developmental effect, improve the microclimate and improve the psychological health of the whole family.

Among the methods of fairy tale therapy for children, telling stories, inventing them together and acting them out are characterized by the fact that they are used most often, which allows them to develop the following characteristics:

- easy and quick behavior correction;
- elimination of fears, phobias, neuroses;
- elimination of negative emotions;
- education of universal human qualities and moral standards;
- education and development;
- for example, the accumulation of experience in the correct attitude to situations.

A feature of psychological fairy tales, especially for children under 3 years of age, is their general cognitive potential. By creating a story with a child about a situation or problem, an adult can gently offer a solution to the problem. The therapeutic effect of their use is very great, it helps to overcome sleep problems in some hyperactive children, expand the child's experience, correctly form the characteristics of attention, expand his thinking, especially in interpersonal relationships, cooperation, harmony, flexibility, listening.

The main feature of advisory and therapeutic activities, widely used in the work of an educational psychologist, is that it has a metaphorical and special style of expression and language. The truth of the event described in the fairy tale is not directly and in the form familiar to listeners, but in a different form. The magic of a fairy tale is determined by the fact that it simultaneously

focuses attention on the mind (in this case, the fairy tale is expressed on the basis of a specific plot with vivid characters), deep, insufficiently understood human structures (fear, experience, complex, passion). While listening to a fairy tale, children compare themselves with the heroes (choose heroes who experience similar difficulties). He does not feel alone in his fears and worries.

Most importantly, seeing how the heroes of fairy tales overcome difficulties, the child gains experience in solving problems and confidence in his abilities. Fairy tales, which are a special educational tool, are also very interesting and valuable for children. We know that a fairy tale comes into the world as a product of human imagination and inner experiences. It is worth noting that they always prioritize humanity, love for the Motherland, honesty and honesty. Experts say that fairy tales expand a child's worldview, form his conscious attitude towards life, and increase his cognitive (mental) capabilities. Through a fairy tale, a child learns to distinguish between good and evil, good and evil. Imprinting this concept into his psychology for life will motivate him to do good deeds after he reaches adulthood.

It is known that telling a fairy tale in an interesting and formal way and thereby attracting the child's attention is also an art. In addition, fairy tales, which are a striking example of folk oral creativity, are not only a means of education, but also bring parents and children together spiritually. That's why experts advise parents to tell their children more stories. After all, one thing should not be forgotten: even if fairy tales are built on the basis of life exaggerations, they naturally reflect the reality of life. These stories, enriched with an interesting plot, help the child consciously understand life. A child who, using the example of fairy tale heroes, learns to overcome dangers even in the most difficult and dangerous situations, grows up mentally and spiritually strong. According to D. Burt, a famous psychologist from Australia, "A child is not only a small person, but also a special person. He reflects his dreams and hopes with the help of magical stories and fairy tales. Indeed, fairy tales, told or read by adults, are one of the psychological factors that form the basis of children's initial self-confidence, sincerity, manners and morality, as well as their intellectual development.

The more children develop self-confidence, the more they overcome their fears, with the help of adults, of course. Listening to fairy tales, children learn the character of fairy-tale heroes with positive images, that is, they imitate them, and also develop the qualities of hatred towards negative heroes, generosity towards weak characters, empathy (sympathy), kindness.

Today, to eliminate fear and anxiety in children, psychologists recommend that parents and teachers effectively use therapeutic methods - fairy tale therapy - one of the most important types of art therapy. In particular, in the field of fairy tale therapy for the prevention and psychocorrection of existing fears of various levels, it is possible to eliminate them by creating

fairy-tale heroes who imagine the situation of fairy-tale heroes and their liberation from this. difficulties resulting from the occurrence of miracles.

Based on the above considerations, it is advisable for psychologists, teachers and parents to follow the following recommendations when telling fairy tales to children: - fairy tales must correspond to the age characteristics of children; - compliance with the individual characteristics of the child, i.e. character, temperament, interests and orientation in the storytelling process; - the essence of the fairy tale, of course, is the victory of good over evil; - presence of principles for solving problems; - the use of paralinguistic (word polishing) methods in the narration process; - and, finally, it is quite natural that a fairy tale should be aimed at eliminating various defects, habits, and fears in children. In conclusion, along with the development of a child's intellectual potential and resourcefulness, a fairy tale serves to help him spend the night in peace and quiet, create wonderful emotional ideas when waking up in the morning, and is important for his spiritually healthy lifestyle. mature and spiritually renewed growth becomes important.

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